

ADVERSITIES AND OBSTACLES IN LEARNING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE IN UZBEKISTAN

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ANNOTATION

This article analyzes facing difficulty to inculcate the skill of second language among students as literary and stylistic device in Modern English language and its morphological characteristics.

Key words: *obstacles, learning, second language educational research, social constructivism, teaching analysis, games theory, qualitative methodologies*

English language plays a vital role in India, so learning English language becomes a relevant factor in the life of each and every Indians and they are well known about the significance of English even though; no one can completely accept the cultural and language differences of English language. Our anxiety towards English language started from the beginning doesn't overcome till now. Many circumstances and related factors are responsible for creating obstacles in learning English. It results, stand like a barrier on the way of students for developing language skills. So we have to eradicate such factors from the way of learners for constructing better future of this language in Uzbek landscape. The vague educational policies, the prejudice outlook towards English, the attitude of parents and teachers, the unfavorable policies of the government, the scarcity of modern teaching technological gadgets in the public sector, the lack of trained language teachers especially in the rural area, the unsuitable syllabi and examination system, the lack of quality teaching training and the deprived position of teachers are the major factors that are arising obstacles in learning English. There are some other factors affecting the process of second language learning such as well-equipped classroom, availability of competent teachers, attitude, motivation, self-

confidence, duration of exposure to the language, family background. Regarding the function of a language, each language has four skills as Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing. The disability or competency over a language varies as the diversity of the socio-linguistic division in this world . The question that should be raised here is from where learners usually get their beliefs about language learning. Different scholars view beliefs differently. Some consider beliefs to be socially constructed, while others deal with as being mental and individual phenomena. Within the field of language learning, beliefs are thought to be of social nature which are constructed and shaped through interactions between groups in a society. Hence, the society's general vision about language learning, the learner's past educational past and personal experiences influences the formation of learners' beliefs and language learning culture. From the period of introduction of English education to the present period, both teachers and students are facing the challenge in English as second language. There are so many obstacles; students are facing to acquire the target language at the maximum level. However everyone must aware the need of learning English for the well-being in their future life, it is a huddle but, have to overcome.

Students tend to learn pronunciation by comparing with their mother tongue. Language transfer designates the interference of the mother tongue in second language learning. Learners apply knowledge from their native language to learn a second language. This can help in understanding and using the target language in some extend, but this can also become a huddle to the proper acquisition of the L2 (second language) rules, syntax (structure), vocabulary, and pronunciation. Krashen has quoted that "syntactic errors in adult performance" occur due to the use of mother tongue in the life of a learner and this impact remains for a long period in the mind of a learner. Learners are influenced by their L1 (mother tongue) in the following manners:

- They apply their first language grammatical knowledge onto the second language which leads to mistakes as a result of structural differences between L1 and L2.
- They pronounce certain sounds incorrectly or with difficulty as a result of the

difference in phonological systems. For e.g.: the actual pronunciation of the word 'forget' is /fəget/ but the students from Malayalam language background used to pronounce like /fəret/ because there is no concept like silent sound in Malayalam.

▪ They confuse vocabulary items because they are misled by the words or phrases that look or sound similar in both the mother tongue and the target language, but differ significantly in meaning. Linguistic interference can lead to correct language production when the mother tongue and the target language share many linguistic features. However, the transfer can result in errors when both languages differ.

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